

A Radical Approach to Exploration: Let the Data Speak for Themselves!

Colin T. Barnett† (SEG 2006), BW Mining, 424 Mapleton Ave., Boulder, Colorado 80304,
and Peter M. Williams,† BW Mining, 28 Eaton Place, Brighton, Sussex, BN2 1EG, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

The most critical decision in exploration is deciding where to look. This decision is often based on partial information rather than quantitative analysis of all the data. We need to put more effort into objective targeting in order to improve the discovery rate. The best way to do this, in sufficiently mature districts, is to use statistical data mining techniques, allowing the data to speak for themselves. The targets generated by this objective approach are highly focused, so that only limited budgets are needed for follow-up investigations. Expected ROIs of many hundreds are achievable.

Those who seek gold dig much earth and find little. — Heraclitus, c. 500 BC

INTRODUCTION

The last 10 to 15 years have seen a significant decline in the rate of new discoveries of valuable mineral deposits. This has happened despite increasing exploration budgets over the same period. Existing gold reserves are being depleted even while the potential profitability of new discoveries is increasing. As Enders and Saunders (2011) point out in their recent thought-provoking article in this newsletter, a radical approach to exploration is urgently needed to offset the falling discovery rate.

The most critical decision in exploration is deciding where to look in the first place. If a good team is put in the right place with modern exploration tools, it will generally succeed and hit the target; in the wrong place, the team will never find anything and simply wastes time and money. Unfortunately, the decision about where to look is too often based on an informal interpretation of partial information rather than quantitative analysis of all the available data. Time and time again, hasty decisions have committed companies to years of wasted effort. If we are to improve the

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†E-mail: colin@bwmining.com, peter@bwmining.com

Courtesy of Government of Western Australia, 1998

FIGURE 1. Geological map of Western Australia showing the outline of the Eastern Goldfields North study area. (see p. 12).

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discovery rate, we need to put more effort into targeting, or deciding where to look.

These same 10 to 15 years have seen a significant growth in the volume of accessible exploration data. To stimulate exploration and mining, regional and national governments are releasing non-proprietary data sets, including geophysics and geochemistry, and compiling databases of known mineral deposits, such as MINEDEX for Western Australia or FINGOLD for Finland. This ever increasing quantity of information is overwhelming to the unaided human interpreter. In future, conventional approaches to exploration will be able to sample only an ever-diminishing fraction of the available information.

Two other relevant developments have taken place over the same period. First, the costs of storage, transfer, and processing of even very large quantities of data have been reduced to a level at which they are no longer significant. Secondly, advances in data mining and statistical pattern recognition now make it possible to extract almost all the relevant information from this wealth of data. In sufficiently mature districts, multivariate correlations between exploration data and known deposits can be used to determine the statistical probabilities of similar economic mineral occurrences at any location in the region.

The targets generated by this approach are based only on measurable exploration data. While such data sets include geology—both lithology and structure—they do not include geological accounts of the ore genesis process. The advantage of the data mining approach, however, is that initial targets are based only on known facts, although insights into the underlying mineralization process can still inform later stages of target ranking or screening. A further advantage of the approach is that, in places where there are good quality data sets, targets are very tightly defined, and they can be assigned probabilities, relative to the available data, from which numerical estimates of expected economic costs and rewards can be derived. For example, integrating the probability field over the target area, with respect to a monetary measure, provides the expected value of a target, relative to the available data. Follow-up exploration costs can be roughly estimated from a target's spatial extent. Since targets are

usually no more than a few square kilometers in area, large expected returns on investment can be achieved.

To explain how statistical data mining works in more detail, we now discuss a particular case study in Western Australia which serves to illustrate all aspects of the approach.

EASTERN GOLDFIELDS NORTH

The Yilgarn craton is so extensive that we chose to limit this study to an area that we call the Eastern Goldfields North (EGN) (see Fig. 1, p. 1). This area falls between longitudes 120°–123°E and latitudes 25°–30°, and extends 300 km east-west by 550 km north-south, making a total of 165,000 km² (to put this in perspective, this is roughly equal to the landmass of the country of Uruguay or the state of Wisconsin). The choice of this particular area was based on various factors—notably, the high concentration of known deposits, the availability of modern exploration data sets, and a stable political environment in which mineral exploration and mining are actively encouraged.

We also deliberately chose to exclude the Super Pit at Kalgoorlie as this deposit is almost 10 times larger than any other deposit in the district. This might dominate the study and overshadow the patterns of some of the smaller but still very significant deposits that occur, and which remain more likely to be found, in this mature district. The EGN contains a known gold endowment of 70 Moz and also provides a large collection of modern exploration data sets. These two critical ingredients make the EGN an excellent candidate for a successful data mining study.

The data sets incorporated in this study were the known gold deposits, regolith mapping, Landsat TM, SRTM elevation, digital geology (lithology and structure), gravity, airborne magnetics and radiometrics, and biogeochemistry. The raw material for all these data sets are in the public domain, so no private or proprietary corporate data sets were used for this data mining study.

Geologic setting

The Eastern Goldfields of Western Australia cover an area of Archean rocks which form part of the Yilgarn craton (see Fig. 1). The major deposits are generally hosted in the greenstone part of

granite-greenstone terrane, particularly in linear belts. They occur in areas of subgreenschist to granulite facies metamorphism, although most significant deposits are in areas of greenschist facies. They occupy diverse structural settings, but are common near major regional shear zones, in secondary faults, and near hinge areas of gently plunging upright antiforms (Cassidy and Hagemann, 2001).

The regolith

A serious impediment to exploration in Western Australia is the regolith, a layer of weathered rock that covers most of the Yilgarn and in particular the EGN study area. It is derived from the chemical and physical weathering of the bedrock over many millions of years, and it can vary from zero or only a few meters to over 150 m thick.

The Geological Survey of Western Australia has produced a seamless regolith map encompassing the entire state (Marnham and Morris, 2003). There are six divisions, ranging from exposed rock to lacustrine deposits. The outcrop areas in the EGN amount to less than 10% of the surface area, so there is little direct geological evidence of the bedrock. However, where the soils appear to be residual rather than widely transported, it is possible to use careful and selective geochemical methods, as we shall see below, to detect mineralization beneath the regolith.

FIGURE 2. Interpreted solid geology (refer to Fig. 1; inset).

Gold endowment

The known gold endowment for the EGN study area is over 70 Moz, while within the Eastern Goldfields as a whole it is around 200 Moz. Several world-class deposits lie outside to the south of the EGN study area. By far the largest is the Super Pit at Kalgoorlie, which alone contains more than 68 Moz. Other notable deposits not covered by this study are St Ives, Norseman, Kanowna Belle, New Celebration, and Mt Charlotte. The EGN study area nonetheless contains 15 known gold deposits with over one Moz of gold, including among them Sunrise Dam, Wallaby, Sons of Gwalia, Agnew, Jundee, Granny Smith, and Tarmoola; and there are another 50 deposits with recorded production of over 30,000 oz.

EXPLORATION DATA

Before commencing the data mining study, we first had to assemble and carefully collimate all the available exploration data sets covering the EGN at a common grid interval. As the data were generally of very high quality, a grid interval of 100 m was chosen for this purpose.

Geology

The geological map that was used for this study came from Geoscience Australia and was published by Liu et al. (2000). This is a 1:500,000 scale solid geology map based on historic 1:100,000 and 1:250,000 scale outcrop mapping combined with interpretation of recent airborne geophysical, gravity, and Landsat TM data. Although this map has only been released in paper form and as an Adobe pdf document, the authors (Alan Whitaker, pers. commun., 2007) were kind enough to provide the map in a digital GIS format that could be input to our data mining study.

This was found to be a highly suitable map for the purposes of this study. In addition to lithology, the map shows structures in the form of faults (major and minor), shear zones (containing strongly deformed rocks), and folds (antiforms and synforms). The lithologic information was represented in a form that captured both individual formations and proximity to contacts between the various formations. The five distinct forms of structure were all separately represented to our data mining study.

Magnetic surveys

Figure 3 shows the aeromagnetic map of the area, which was also obtained from

FIGURE 3. Magnetic intensity image.

FIGURE 4. Bouguer gravity image.

Geoscience Australia (Percival, 2010). This map was compiled from about 10 modern surveys that had been flown since the early 1990s. The line spacing of these surveys ranged from 200 to 400 m, and the flying height ranged from 60 to 100 m. The data quality is therefore extremely good—in fact, much better than in many other parts of the world.

Data were reduced to the pole to center the anomalies over any causative magnetic bodies. The data range of the map shown in Figure 3 is over 10,000 nanoteslas, which is unusually high but not too surprising considering the number of banded iron formations and granitic intrusions present in this area.

Gravity

Figure 4 shows the gravity map of the area, which was produced from a grid provided by Geoscience Australia (Wynne and Bacchin, 2009). The data range for this map is 800 gravity units (or 80 milligals). These data had been collected in many small ground surveys, starting in the 1950s when sensitive gravimeters first became available. The average station spacing in the EGN is around 4 km, which is adequate for our purposes. In the next few years, no doubt a modern airborne gravity survey will be carried out, which should provide even better data with more uniform coverage.

Radiometric studies

The radiometric data used for this project came from Geoscience Australia, and were collected in the last 20 years in conjunction with the aeromagnetic

data described above. The data came from 10 different surveys (Percival, 2010), which have been blended into separate grids of potassium, uranium, and thorium counts.

Figure 5 shows a ternary K-U-Th image of the radiometric data. It can be seen that this image correlates nicely with the geology shown in Figure 2. The granites are typically high in potassium and therefore generally map as reddish colors. And, despite the regolith cover, the greenstone belts stand out as bluish-green zones trending NNW across the area. This is very encouraging as it means the

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FIGURE 5. Radiometric ternary image.

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radiometrics, which are normally considered a shallow-penetrating tool, are clearly reflecting the bedrock geology and geochemistry through the surface weathering. Presumably the regolith has been in place without much change for millions of years, which has allowed time for key elements to trickle up to the surface.

Geochemistry

Various forms of geochemistry were considered for inclusion in the study. These included lithochemochemistry from the Australian National Geochemistry Database (Budd et al., 2002), as well as hydrogeochemistry and biogeochemistry from two recent Minerals and Energy Research Institute of Western Australia (MERIWA) projects (Gray et al., 2009; Reid et al., 2010).

Lithochemochemistry was found to be too sparsely sampled to be useful. Also, the samples tended to be concentrated in and around the pits of the gold and nickel deposits with big (50 km) gaps in between. This resulted in a strong correlation with the known mineralization but made the data of little practical use as a predictor. The hydrogeochemistry was more evenly sampled from the numerous water bores in this area, but it had a very weak correlation with the known gold deposits. This may be due to transport of elements in the groundwater, reportedly as much as 10 km in the direction of flow, and also perhaps because of the extremely low analytic levels of the various elements.

The biogeochemistry, on the other hand, which was based on sampling the leaves of mulga trees close to the boreholes tested in the hydrogeochemistry survey, proved to have a very good correlation with the known gold deposits. A total of 56 elements, of which just one example (gold) is shown in Figure 6, were gridded and passed to the data mining process. The only limitation of the biogeochemistry is that the survey did not cover the entire area of our EGN study. This meant, of course, that target predictions incorporating these data could only be made where there was complete data coverage.

Landsat

A data set that is readily obtainable in any part of the world is the Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM). In some arid terranes, like the Walker Lane of Nevada

FIGURE 6. Biogeochemistry gold image.

and the Altiplano of Chile, these data are highly useful for directly mapping mineral alteration systems. We therefore acquired these data in the hope that they might also be helpful in the Eastern Goldfields. In this region, however, the TM data were found to be merely reflecting the regolith. Furthermore, the TM data are extremely sensitive to man-made disturbances. The known gold (and nickel) mines and their associated waste dumps stand out very conspicuously in all the TM bands. Experiments quickly showed that these data were not discriminating at detecting mineralization and therefore could not be used for this purpose in the EGN.

Topography

Another data set that is widely available is the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) global elevation data. These data were collected during a single 11-day space mission in February 2000, and now provide high-resolution coverage of 80% of the earth's surface. In many parts of the world the terrain map can be a useful indicator of local structure and lithology. Linear ridge crest and drainage patterns may indicate faults, while circular patterns may indicate diapirs. Siliceous rocks tend to resist weathering and form high ground. In this area, however, the terrain is largely reflecting the regolith and does not tell us much about the bedrock geology. Also, the pits tend to form distinctive, conical-shaped holes in the terrain. When trained to correlate

the known gold deposits with the SRTM data, the data mining process promptly picked out all the nickel pits! Although this was a convincing demonstration of the power of the data mining process, it was hardly useful in predicting other, as yet undisturbed, gold deposits.

Known deposits

The Geological Survey of Western Australia produces an annually updated map of all the known deposits in the state (Cooper et al., 2007). However, in common with the data in the national OZMIN database (Ewers et al., 2002), it is not sufficiently accurate for data mining purposes. Many of the deposits are located only approximately, sometimes up to a couple of kilometers away from the actual mine site. In order to work at a 100 m grid interval, it is necessary to know the precise location or actual footprints of the deposits.

Fortunately, most of the major listed deposits are shallow enough to have been exploited by open pit. In this semi-arid terrain with its minimal, shrubby vegetation, the open pits show up very clearly from space. The pits thus reveal the precise location of the gold mineralization as the miners were generally careful not to move much barren rock except as necessary laybacks to the pits.

Figure 7 shows a satellite image of the Bronzewing gold mine downloaded from Google Earth. The scene is dominated by the tailings to the east, but two open pits can clearly be seen on the western side of this image. The Discovery Pit is to the south and the smaller Central Pit is to the north.

Such Google Earth (GE) images represent a mosaic of many small images tied together by control points on the ground. Most of these were found to be quite accurate, but one was conspicuously misregistered by several hundred meters. Another way of mapping the pits is to use the SRTM elevation data, which are precisely positioned. We therefore primarily used the SRTM data, supplemented by the GE data in the case of a few recent discoveries that postdate the Shuttle Mission in 2000.

We also drew on company reports for the locations of a few underground deposits, such as the Darlot Centenary mine, which did not commence operations as open pits. In this fashion, it was possible to locate and digitize the surface projections of 240 discrete gold

FIGURE 7. Google Earth image of Bronzewing gold mine.

deposits in the EGN. These accurate footprints were then used to train the neural networks as described in the next section.

There are, of course, also thousands of old workings with little or no recorded production. However, these were not used for training purposes since the aim is only to discover further economic deposits. A study such as this should be able to distinguish the two. It happens that several of our high ranking targets lie near abandoned shafts or small diggings; but the majority of such old workings are not found to be favorable.

DATA MINING

The data mining process used for this study is based on probabilistic modeling with neural networks and is described in greater detail in Barnett and Williams (2006, 2008).

The primary layers of exploration data used as input to the neural networks were gravity and magnetics, lithology and structure, radiometrics and biogeochemistry. However, there is little meaning in a single-point geophysical, or for that matter, geological reading. It is the pattern around a given station that is important. Such patterns can be represented by taking the derivatives of the primary data—for example, gravity—and inputting these as well to the neural networks. For completeness, it is necessary to take the horizontal, vertical, and cross-derivatives, and to include both first-and second-order terms. This results

in nine extra secondary layers derived from each primary layer. Similarly, it is necessary to take account of proximity to geological contacts and structures, and of their strikes. The total number of layers assembled for this project came to over 250, representing about 15 Gb of gridded data files.

Before embarking on a full integration of the data, it can be instructive to examine individual data sets, to help determine which are contributing most to the final target map. Some data sets are evidently more informative than others in relation to economic gold occurrence, and the statistical approach allows such differences to be quantified. In the EGN study, biogeochemistry and geological structure prove, individually, to be the most relevant data sets, followed closely by gravity and lithology. Radiometric data come next, with magnetic data being the least relevant. Nonetheless, a data set may be only moderately relevant on its own, but can make a worthwhile contribution in combination with others. The results shown below are based on a combination of all the data.

Discussion of results

Figure 8 shows a close-up of a typical target resulting from our data mining study. Note that the scale bar now represents 5 km, which is a 20-fold zoom on the 100 km scale shown in all the previous figures. In this particular area, there are five historic workings which produced over 500,000 oz of gold. The process suggests that there is still more gold to be found close to one of the old

workings on the east side of this map. The main red target zone is about 500 m wide and about 2,500 m long, which could represent a significant deposit.

Figure 9 shows the corresponding geological map of this area. It can be seen that the target occurs in mafic greenstone rocks close to a shear zone containing granite gneiss. Four of the five

FIGURE 9. Closeup of the target geology.

historic workings lie on regional structures, while the fifth occurs within an ultramafic unit. The new target indicated by the neural network also coincides with an ultramafic unit. It would be a relatively straightforward matter to follow up this target in the field with geologic mapping, regolith geochemistry, and exploratory drilling, if the results are positive.

The EGN study produced more than a dozen such high priority targets which merit further follow-up work. While some are genuinely new, separate, and sizeable areas of high favorability, the majority of these targets occur in established camps within a few kilometers of operating or historic gold mines. The odds are high that several of these targets will prove to be economic deposits of gold.

STATISTICAL ISSUES

The EGN study used nonlinear statistical models known as artificial neural networks. Neural networks can be used to model arbitrarily complex relations between inputs and outputs. A suitably fitted model takes, as input, the exploration data surrounding any given location—

FIGURE 8. Closeup of a typical target.

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represented, in our case, by up to 250 numbers—and generates, as output, the favorability at that location.

If the network is fitted using equal numbers of gold and non-gold occurrences, and minimizes a suitable error function, subject to regularization such as Williams (1995), its output approximates the weight of evidence *W* in favor of an economic gold occurrence at any given location. This is the log ratio of its posterior odds to its prior odds:

$$W = \log \left\{ \frac{p}{(1-p)} / \frac{p_0}{(1-p_0)} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where *p*₀ is the prior probability of the event and *p* is its posterior probability.¹ The *posterior* odds *p*/(1 - *p*) are based on the local exploration data. The *prior* odds *p*₀/(1 - *p*₀) are the odds of finding gold at a random location; by throwing a dart at the map, for example.

Probability

In our approach, *W* is modeled directly without making assumptions about the prior *p*₀. This is an important feature since only the *W*-scores are needed to define exploration targets. Economic analysis, however, needs probabilities. That means assuming a value for *p*₀ and then solving (1) for *p* in terms of *W*.

The economic analysis below assumes that there is one-quarter as much gold still to be found as has already been found. In support of this, a recent study (Guj et al., 2011) concluded that 75% of the gold endowment of the whole Yilgarn craton had probably been discovered by 2008. If the same holds for the EGN, then the assumption that 80% has now been found—so that a quarter of the existing inventory remains to be found—is not overly optimistic. Comparing the total area of deposit footprints to the total area of the region, this leads to a prior *p*₀ = 0.000625.

¹This concept and terminology date back to Alan Turing's cryptanalytic work during the Second World War. The exploration community may know the term better through the more recent work of writers such as Graeme Bonham-Carter. It is important, however, not to confuse the concept with the way it is calculated. In our view, the usual so-called "weights of evidence" approach to calculating this quantity has serious shortcomings compared with the present approach, arising from its restricted forms of data representation and its need for exploration data sets to be statistically independent.

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

The statistical data mining approach not only identifies targets, it provides estimates of quantities needed for economic analysis. These include the ideas of cost, risk, and reward (Mackenzie, 1998; Singer and Kouda, 1999; Lord et al., 2001). For example, the expected value of a target can be defined as the product of the target value and the probability of success, less the cost of advancing the project to the next stage of exploration (Mackenzie, 1998).

Target ranking

Targets were identified by selecting regions where the weight of evidence *W* exceeds 5, when using logarithms to base 2. The top 10 targets are shown in Table 1. The *W*-max columns show the peak values achieved over each target. The extent of each target is defined as the area, within 700 m of the peak, where *W* exceeds 5. The area column shows this extent measured in hectares—in other words, in terms of the number of 100 m grid cells it contains. For example, Target 1 has an area of 1.44 km².

The quantity in the size column is defined as follows. The local weight of evidence *W* determines the probability that a location lies within the footprint of a mineable economic deposit. The quantity displayed in the size column of Table 1 is the sum of these posterior probabilities over the 100 m grid points included in the target area.

Target value

The size column in Table 1 can be used to calculate the expected monetary value of a target as follows. The present known gold endowment of the study area, the EGN, is more than 70 Moz. The total

area of the footprints of the pits or underground operations from which this resource has been, or will be, extracted is approximately 15 km². This means that, where economic gold deposits occur in the EGN, they occur on average with an abundance of approximately 5 Moz per km², or 50 Koz per hectare. Assuming that future discoveries will have the same average abundance, the probability that a 100 m grid point is within the footprint of a mineable economic deposit is the probability that the cell it represents has a resource of 50 Koz. By summing these probabilities over the target area, to obtain the size values shown in Table 1, and then multiplying by 50,000, we obtain the expected value of the target in ounces. If this is multiplied by the net dollar return per ounce, we obtain the expected value in dollars. This is shown in the value column of Table 2 assuming, for illustration, a net return of \$500 per oz. Using these figures, the highest ranking target, for example, has an expected value of \$294M.

It should be emphasized that figures in the value column of Table 2 are not estimates of actual resources, assuming they exist, but *expected values*, in the sense of products of possible rewards and the probabilities of obtaining them. Furthermore, these expectations are based only on regional exploration data. They would change with the addition of further information such as might be obtained from drilling or, ultimately, mining. At the initial exploration stage, however, that information is not available, so that these are the relevant figures when making initial decisions.

TABLE 1. The Top Ten Targets of the Data Mining Study*

Target no.	Size	Area (ha)	W-max
1	11.77	144	8.69
2	8.15	136	7.93
3	7.50	148	7.30
4	6.83	134	6.74
5	6.67	133	6.98
6	6.46	134	7.53
7	5.81	146	7.24
8	4.10	90	7.21
9	4.03	86	7.98
10	3.94	90	7.33

*See text for explanation of size, area, and W-max calculations

TABLE 2. Table Showing Expected Values and Costs Associated with the Ten Highest Ranked Targets*

Target no.	Value \$M	Cost \$K	Prob %
1	294	720	20.6
2	204	680	13.3
3	187	740	8.9
4	171	670	11.3
5	167	665	10.2
6	161	670	10.4
7	145	730	8.7
8	103	450	8.5
9	101	430	13.7
10	99	450	9.1
Total	\$1.6B	\$6.2M	

*See text for explanation of value, cost, and probability (Prob) calculations

Target cost

It is difficult to estimate the cost of investigating a target in advance. Limited low cost investigations may be enough to exclude a target. Otherwise, investigation will be a sequential process of increasing cost, possibly involving geochemistry, geophysics, rotary air blast and core drilling. Despite this, we shall assume for definiteness that the cost per target is proportional to its area; specifically, that the cost is \$500K per km², or \$5K per hectare. Using the target areas shown in Table 1, the resulting cost estimates for the top 10 targets are shown in the cost column of Table 2.

Target probability

The concepts of Value and Cost are already enough for initial economic decisions. For example, in the case of Target 1, the ROI (return on investment = expected gain divided by cost) exceeds 400. It is natural, nonetheless, to ask for the probability of success for each target as a whole. The present study, however, does not directly model the probability that an extended area hosts a deposit; rather, it models the probability that a given location is within the footprint of a mineable economic deposit. All the same, the peak probability over the target area is a lower bound on the probability of success for the target as a whole; so that this is shown in the probability column of Table 2, on the understanding that it may be an underestimate. For example, there is at least a 20% chance that the highest ranked target hosts an economic deposit.

Multiple targets

The rows of Table 2 relate to the risks and rewards for individual targets. But clearly an exploration strategy that tested multiple targets, consecutively or concurrently, would improve the overall chance of a discovery. For example, if the top 10 targets are tested, the probability of making at least one discovery is at least 70%; for at least two discoveries, it is at least 32%.

As the totals in Table 2 show, the budget needed to investigate the top 10 targets is a little over \$6.2M. The expected gain—that is to say, the sum of possible rewards multiplied by their probabilities—is \$1.6 billion. The return on investment for a program that follows up just the top 10 targets is therefore greater than 250.

CONCLUSIONS

As Enders and Saunders (2011) have pointed out, a new approach to exploration is needed to offset the falling discovery rate. We believe that one way to address this problem is to put more effort into the targeting process. The probability of making a discovery is the product of the probability p that a deposit exists and the probability q of finding it, assuming that it exists. Much effort in recent years has gone into improving q , resulting in great strides in modern exploration tools. However, there has been scant change in the targeting process, which can strongly impact probability p .

In this article, we have proposed a data mining process which takes advantage of all the available data in a given area. A critical aspect of this approach is its proper and complete representation of the data. The statistical process can then integrate hundreds of possibly interdependent data layers, with each making its own appropriate statistically determined contribution. The outcome is a sharply focused target map that assigns numerical probabilities of making an economic discovery. This map can then be used for systematically ranking and rating targets and planning a cost-effective followup program.

This approach will naturally work best in mature districts like the EGN where there is a wealth of known deposits and multidisciplinary data. In other parts of the world where there may be less data, the data mining approach will still provide benefits although it may not produce such sharply focused targets. Fortunately, there is now an encouraging trend to produce more such comprehensive data sets as governments globally around the world increasingly appreciate that this is the best way to stimulate exploration and mineral development in their own countries.

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REFERENCES

- Barnett, C.T., and Williams, P.M., 2006, Mineral exploration using modern data mining techniques: Society of Economic Geologists Special Publication 12, p. 295–310.
- 2008, The data mining approach to target generation in mature districts, *in* Milkereit, B., ed., *Exploration in the new millennium: Proceedings of the 5th Decennial International Conference on Mineral Exploration*, Toronto, Canada, September 9–12, 2007, www.dmec.ca/ex07-dvd/E07/pdfs/34.pdf, p. 513–524.
- Budd, A.R., Hazell, M., Sedgmen, A., and Sedgmen, L., (Kilgour, B., compiler), 2002, OZCHEM national whole rock geochemistry database: Canberra, The Commonwealth of Australia, Geoscience Australia, www.ga.gov.au/meta/ANZCW0703011055.html.
- Cassidy, K.F., and Hagemann, S.G., 2001, “World-class” Archean orogenic gold deposits, eastern Yilgarn craton: Diversity in timing, structural controls and mineralization styles: Geoscience Australia, Record 2001/37, p. 382–384.
- Cooper, R.W., Abeysinghe, P.B., and Flint, D.J., compilers, 2007, Western Australia atlas of mineral deposits and petroleum fields 2007: Western Australia Geological Survey, 48p.
- Enders, M.S., and Saunders, C., 2011, Discovery, innovation, and learning in the mining business—new ways forward for an old industry: SEG Newsletter, no. 86, p. 1, 16–22.
- Ewers, G.R., Evans, N., and Hazell, M. (Kilgour, B., compiler), 2002, OZMIN mineral deposits database: Canberra, The Commonwealth of Australia, Geoscience Australia, www.ga.gov.au/meta/ANZCW0703003393.html.
- Gray, D., Noble, R., and Reid, N., 2009, Hydrogeochemical mapping of northeast Yilgarn groundwater (MERIWA): Geological Survey of Western Australia, Record 2009/21, 78 p.
- Guj, P., Fallon, M., McCuaig, T.C., and Fagan, R., 2011, A time-series audit of Zipf’s law as a measure of terrane endowment and maturity in mineral exploration: *Economic Geology*, v. 106, p. 241–259.
- Liu, S.F., Stewart, A.J., Farrell, T.R., Whitaker, A.J., and Chen, S.F., 2000, Solid Geology of the North Eastern Goldfields, Western Australia (1:500,000 scale map), ACT: AGSO, www.ga.gov.au/meta/ANZCW0703003267.html.
- Lord, D., Etheridge, M., Willson, M., Hall, G., and Uttley, P., 2001, Measuring exploration success: An alternate to the discovery cost-per-ounce method of quantifying exploration effectiveness: SEG Newsletter, no. 45, p. 1, 10–16.
- Mackenzie, B.W., 1998, Economic evaluations for mineral investment decisions: Glenside, South Australia, Australian Mineral Foundation, Short Course Notes, 2 volumes.
- Marnham, J., and Morris, P.A., 2003, A seamless digital regolith map of Western Australia: A potential resource for mineral exploration and environmental management: Western Australia Geological Survey, Annual Review 2002-03, p. 27–33 (1:500,000 scale map and digital data sets).
- Percival, P.J., 2010, Index of airborne geophysical surveys (eleventh edition): Geoscience Australia, Record 2010/13, 297 p.
- Reid, N., Lintern, M., Anand, R., Pinchand, T., Gray, D., Noble, R., Sutton, G., and Jarrett, R., 2010, North East Yilgarn biogeochemistry project (MERIWA): Geological Survey of Western Australia, Record 2010/4, 154 p.
- Singer, D.A., and Kouda, R., 1999, Examining risk in mineral exploration: *Natural Resources Research*, v. 8, p. 111–122.
- Williams, P.M., 1995, Bayesian regularization and pruning using a Laplace prior: *Neural Computation*, v. 7, p. 117–143.
- Wynne, P., and Bacchin, M., 2009, Index of gravity surveys (second edition): Geoscience Australia, Record 2009/07, p. xvi + 1832.